

A stabilized finite element framework for anisotropic adaptive topology optimization of incompressible fluid flows

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Abstract

Shape or topology optimization, aims to find the most convenient material distribution in order to minimize a given criteria, that is the cost function. In this work, we will demonstrate our application of topology optimization based on the Level Set method for reducing head losses. Anisotropic mesh adaptation was applied to capture the interface, and the sensitivity was calculated based on the continuous adjoint method. Three numerical examples were given, where we seek on one hand to validate the algorithm, and on the other hand, to demonstrate the effect of the starting geometry on the final shape.

Keywords: Topology Optimization, Level Set Method, Continuous Adjoint, Anisotropic Mesh Adaptation

1. Introduction

Nowadays, with the increase of energy prices, and the increase of the environmental impact of the energy consuming systems, in parallel with the wish of the state to become less energy dependent, the industry is driving research towards reducing the energy consumption of their products by optimizing their energy systems to increase their efficiency.

Bendsøe and Sigmund [1] identified three methods of optimization: parametric, geometric, and topology optimization. Each of these methods is characterized by the architecture of the initial design and the procedure that we follow to reach the final design. Our concern in this work will be about topology optimization.

Topology optimization techniques allow not only to change the size or shape of a structure but also its topology or architecture. In other words, they may result in modifying the connectivity between the inlets

and the outlets, and also the connectivity between the fluid ducts that may be in the system by merging already existing ducts or nucleating more of them. This being said, a major advantage of topology optimization techniques is their ability to generate a physical non trivial design without providing them with an initial design or architecture. We can for example begin with a fluid filled design domain, or maybe solid filled domain, or even a combination of both of them.

The density method and the Level Set method are the leading methods for topology optimization[2]. Both methods rely on determining fluid and solid regions. While the density method deals with the entire domain at once, the Level-Set method deals only with surface sensitivities. While the first is faster, more general and less dependant on the initial geometry, the second leads by its ability to generate manufacturable designs with well defined fluid-solid interfaces.

In this paper, we aim to build a numerical framework for topology optimization with hydraulic ap-

plications. Thus, we will first talk about the classic level-set method for interface capturing, then we will explain how we applied automatic anisotropic mesh adaptation to increase the computation precision near the interface and reduce instabilities. Then we will talk about the mixing laws that generate the fluid properties that goes into an Incompressible Navier-Stokes solver. We will also show the weak formulation of the solver with the variational multi-scale approach. After, we will explain the derivation of the convected level-set solver, a powerful tool to precisely transport the interface to the desired position. Then we will talk about the adjoint solver, with the derivation and computation of the control velocity that will be later-on the drive variable of the advection solver. Finally, technical modifications will also be applied: the surface constraint, and the softblocking of the connections with the inlets and outlets. A numerical benchmark will be exhibited in order to validate our framework and prove its effectiveness. Finally we will end up with a conclusion and some perspectives.

2. Numerical Framework

2.1. Eulerian Framework

The level-set method has been used to implicitly track the interface within an Eulerian context. For shape optimization, it consists on separating the fluid regions from the solid ones by a signed distance function α whose zero isovalues correspond to the fluid-solid interface. Let us define Ω the whole computational domain, Ω_{fluid} the fluid domain, and Ω_{solid} the solid domain, and let us denote by $\Gamma_{int} = \Omega_{fluid} \cap \Omega_{solid}$ the interface between them. The level-set function represents the shortest distance to the interface Γ , it is defined at each node x of the domain Ω as follows:

$$\alpha(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha(x, t) = -dist(x, \Gamma_{int}) & \text{if } x \in \Omega_{fluid} \\ \alpha(x, t) = 0 & \text{if } x \in \Gamma_{int} \\ \alpha(x, t) = +dist(x, \Gamma_{int}) & \text{if } x \in \Omega_{solid} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Anisotropic Mesh Adaptation

Anisotropic mesh adaptation allows us to increase the accuracy of capturing the interface. Indeed, since the level set is an implicit definition of the interface, its zero iso-value intersects the elements of the mesh arbitrarily. As a consequence, discontinuities due to the high ratio in the physical properties between the solid and the fluid may lead to numerical oscillations during the resolution of PDEs. Instead, we will consider a regularized interface, meaning that the properties are distributed smoothly over a minimal thickness around

the interface. Using anisotropic mesh adaptation with highly stretched elements will help reducing the interface thickness, and will increase the accuracy of the computation due to a higher mesh resolution. To obtain an accurate description of the interface using the level set function, we consider the normal direction as the principal direction of mesh refinement. The anisotropic mesh adaptation procedure is performed using a metric map that prescribes a mesh size according to the principal directions in the domain. These principal directions are given by the eigenvectors of this metric and the mesh size is related to the eigenvalues of this metric. And in order to build the corresponding metric, we start by setting up the error estimator that is according to [3] can then be written as:

$$\|\nabla q_h \cdot x^{ij} - \nabla q(x^i) \cdot x^{ij}\| \leq \max_{y \in [x^i, x^j]} |\nabla^2 q(y) x^{ij} \cdot x^{ij}| \quad (2)$$

Then, as proved in [4], and since for $P1$ finite elements on anisotropic meshes edge residuals dominate a posteriori errors, it is suitable to define an error indicator function e^{ij} associated to the edge x^{ij} as:

$$e^{ij} = |g^{ij} \cdot x^{ij}| \quad (3)$$

However, the gradient is not known at the vertices, thus a recovery procedure has to be considered, The recovered gradient G^i is the solution of the following optimization problem:

$$G^i = \arg \min_G \left(\sum_{j \in \Gamma(i)} |(G - \nabla q_h) \cdot x^{ij}|^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

whose solution leads us to as estimation error expressed as:

$$e_{ij} = G^{ij} \cdot x^{ij} \quad (5)$$

In order to relate the error estimation to mesh adaptation, we will introduce a stretching factor s^{ij} defined as the ratio between the length of the edges x^{ij} before and after the adaptation procedure. The stretching factor s^{ij} of the edge ij is chosen so that the total number of nodes in the mesh is kept fixed and is defined as

$$s^{ij} = \left(\frac{e_{ij}}{e(N)} \right) \quad (6)$$

Finally, the metric takes the following expression[5]:

$$M^i = (\tilde{X}^i)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where \tilde{X}^i is defines as:

$$\tilde{X}^i = \frac{1}{|\Gamma_i|} \left(\sum_{j \in \Gamma(i)} s^{ij} \times x^{ij} \right) \quad (8)$$

Figure 1: Progressive zoom on the mesh at the interface of the converged solution of the Bend Pipe design

In the following work, the only adaptation criterion will be the interface separating the fluid and solid regions, characterized by the truncated distance function. Figure 1 shows a progressive zoom in on the interface of a converged solution of a test case in section 5. At the left and right sides of the interface, we imposed a constant error in order to eliminate mesh adaptation in these regions and generate an isotropic mesh of constant mesh size. Since no computation is made in the solid region, we set a very small error that thus generates a very coarse mesh. And inversely, we set a relatively larger error in the fluid domain to generate a finer mesh.

2.3. Incompressible Navier-Stokes Solver

So we will consider the following velocity-pressure formulation of the non-linear Navier-Stokes equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(p, \mathbf{u}) &= 0 & \text{in } \Omega_{fluid} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 & \text{in } \Omega_{fluid} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where p and \mathbf{u} are the pressure and the velocity, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the stress tensor which reads:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = 2\mu\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) - p\mathbf{I}_d \quad (10)$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity, \mathbf{I}_d is the identity tensor and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ the strain-rate tensor defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) \quad (11)$$

The complete description of the variational multiscale (VMS) formulation can be found in [5] and [6].

2.4. Level Set Convection

2.4.1. Standard level set method

Classically, the motion of the interface results from the following advection equation[7]:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\alpha(x, t) = \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \alpha = 0 \quad (12)$$

An interesting feature on using a distance function is that we may ensure the smoothness of the quantity to be convected, which is very important when solving an advection equation with the finite element method. In fact, despite the latest improvements in stabilization techniques, the gradient smoothness remains a key point for having a stable scheme, since $\|\nabla \alpha\| = 1$ is not ensured by just solving 12. Owing to the flow complexity, the gradient of α can become very steep and numerical instabilities may occur. Thus, it is necessary to reinitialize the distance function. Classically, reinitialization is obtained by solving a Hamilton–Jacobi equation that reconstructs the level set with the exact zero isovalue of $\alpha(x, t)$ [8]. If we introduce a virtual time τ , we search $\gamma(x, \tau)$ that has the same zero values than $\alpha(x, t)$:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \tau} + s(\alpha)(\|\nabla \gamma\| - 1) = 0 \quad (13)$$

where $s(\alpha)$ is the sign function of α .

Equation 13 can be rewritten as an another advection equation:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \gamma = s(\alpha) \quad (14)$$

with the velocity \mathbf{U} computed as:

$$\mathbf{U} = s(\alpha) \frac{\nabla \gamma}{\|\nabla \gamma\|} \quad (15)$$

The Hamilton–Jacobi procedure being iterative, the computational cost induced can be prohibitive for large computations. A method to alleviate this burden is the so-called convected level set method.

2.4.2. Convected level set method

The main idea of the convective re-initialization is to avoid the re-initialization step of the standard level-set method[9]. For this purpose, a parameter λ is introduced as:

$$\lambda = \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial t} \quad (16)$$

Thus we have:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial t} = \lambda \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \tau} \quad (17)$$

And we can rewrite equation 13 to obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial t} + \lambda s(\alpha)(\|\nabla \gamma\| - 1) = 0 \quad (18)$$

Since we are in an Eulerian context, the time derivative can be changed in total derivative. Consequently, when using again α as the main variable, and substituting with 12, we finally get the convected re-initialization equation below:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \alpha + \lambda s(\alpha)(\|\nabla \alpha\| - 1) = 0 \quad (19)$$

Re-written as:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} + \lambda \mathbf{U}) \cdot \nabla \alpha = \lambda s(\alpha) \quad (20)$$

2.4.3. Local distance function

The only useful information for our computation is the exact zero isovalue position. Thus, the complete domain level set advection is not necessary, and may be the cause of further numerical instabilities. Another idea is to cut off the level set function at a thickness E using an hyperbolic tangent filter. The truncated level set, denoted $\hat{\alpha}$, is:

$$\hat{\alpha}(\alpha) = E \tanh\left(\frac{\alpha}{E}\right) \quad (21)$$

where E is the cut-off thickness.

The truncated level set now verifies the following property:

$$\|\nabla \hat{\alpha}\| = 1 - \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}}{E}\right)^2 \quad (22)$$

And by substitution, the final and only equation to solve now reads:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} + \lambda \mathbf{U}) \cdot \nabla \alpha = \lambda s(\alpha) \left(1 - \left(\frac{\hat{\alpha}}{E}\right)^2\right) \quad (23)$$

It is shown in [10] that the proposed method reduces the computational cost and ensure a better mass conservation than the classical level set method.

2.5. Control variable and Objective Function

The control variable of the optimization problem is chosen to be the normal velocity of the fluid-solid interface. This velocity is indeed an input to the advection solver (ref section 2.5) that updates the position of the level-set function. Numerically, and with a fixed time-step, this velocity characterises the normal displacement of the interface as shown in figure 2. Here,

Figure 2: The deformation of the starting geometry (solid line) to the new one (dashed line) causes the total variation in the displacement, which depends on the flow variables

it is important to note that the value of the control velocity does not necessarily indicate the distance that the interface should travel. It is instead a comparative value of the relative displacement between each node and its neighbor. This being said, the convergence criteria is an equal control variable on all the interface rather than particularly a zero control velocity.

In the next section, we will investigate how to find an expression of the control velocity, that moves the interface in a way to minimize a certain objective function. For the rest of the work, we will deal with the following objective function:

$$J = \int_{\Gamma_{in} \cup \Gamma_{out}} \left(p + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{u}\|^2 \right) \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} d(\Gamma_{in} \cup \Gamma_{out}) \quad (24)$$

which characterizes the minimization of the total power dissipated by a fluid dynamic device.

2.6. Adjoint solver and sensitivity analysis

Based on the continuous adjoint method for sensitivity analysis, the adjoint system that we derived is:

$$\begin{cases} -(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \hat{\mathbf{u}} + \nabla \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}} - \nabla \cdot \sigma(-\hat{p}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}) = 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ and \hat{p} are respectively the adjoint velocity and adjoint pressure.

We can easily notice that it is very similar to the Navier-Stokes equations, with two exceptions: the convection term is linear and is followed by the *minus* sign which switches the physical inlets and outlets for the adjoint problem, and we have an additional production term (Second term in equation 25). This is an additional advantage since we've been based on the Navier-Stokes solver to solve the adjoint equations. One main difference is that the adjoint equations are linear, and thus we do not need iterative models to get converged solutions.

The adjoint boundary conditions for equation (25) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_n &= -\mathbf{u}_{in} \cdot \mathbf{n} & \text{on } & \Gamma_{in} \\ \hat{u}_t &= 0 & \text{on } & \Gamma_{in} \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}} &= \mathbf{0} & \text{on } & \Gamma_{wall} \cup \Omega_{solid} \\ \sigma(-\hat{p}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}) \cdot \mathbf{n} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \hat{\mathbf{u}} &= \mathbf{0} & \text{on } & \Gamma_{out} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where the subscripts n and t refer respectively to the normal and tangential components of the vector that holds them.

The control velocity is therefore, a combination of the state and adjoint variables, and is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}_c = \frac{\partial J}{\partial \beta} = \mu [(\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla) u_t \cdot (\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla) \hat{u}_t] \mathbf{n} \quad (27)$$

For practical reasons, both the primal and the dual systems are solved in the entire design domain Ω . As a result, the control velocity is also computed at every node of the design domain. Whereas, the expression of the derived sensitivity is only valid near the solid-fluid interface. Also, in some cases, it may happen that the maximum of this gradient is not localised on the fluid-solid interface. This may be blurring, since the maximum gradient is the main criteria that affects the numerical stability of the advection solver. A trivial solution was to implement a Dirac model, whose equation is shown below:

$$D(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2e} [1 + \cos(\frac{\pi \alpha}{e})] & \text{if } |\alpha| < e \\ 0 & \text{if } else \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

The Dirac model vanishes the value of the control velocity on all the nodes far from the interface. And a numerical treatment, creates a set of binary values that are *True* on a thickness e centered on the fluid-solid interface. This allows us to avoid oscillations, while keeping a maximum of deformation per iteration. And thus, it also allows us to accelerate the convergence of the result without losing in precision.

Finally, for numerical stability purposes, the calculated gradient is multiplied by a descent factor before it is attributed to the advection solver. But this descent factor is very problematic, because the order of magnitude of the calculated gradient changes with the shape's evolution. With this being said, a fixed step deformation, even if relatively well adapted, causes fluctuations in the rate of shape deformation. To remedy, we implemented an algorithm that re-scales the control velocity, by multiplying it with coefficients that oblige its maximum to oscillate between 0.1 and 1. At the end, this re-scaled velocity is multiplied by a descent factor, set by the user depending on the case,

and specially depending on the fictive time step of the advection solver.

3. Technical Modifications

After we built the main framework for topology optimization, some technical modifications are necessary for good functioning of the algorithm: a surface constraint and soft-blocking of the connections.

3.1. Surface Constraint

Previous work shows that, for some objective functions, the optimal shape tends to one of two extreme cases: either fill all the design domain (that is for example the case of pressure drop minimization), or completely disappear (that is the case of drag reduction). Though theoretically correct, the two extremes cases are undesired in the industrial field. For that reason, we put in place a surface constraint that keeps the geometry on a constant surface.

For that, we start by computing the fluid surface. For maximum precision, the surface calculation is done by integrating a Heaviside model on the solid domain. Then we subtract this value from the design domain surface to get the surface of the fluid region. Then, after each deformation, we add an offset value to the distance function ($\alpha = \alpha \pm \delta$), that allows us to recover our desired surface without affecting the geometry's shape. Then, after each deformation, we add an offset value to the distance function, that allows us to recover our desired surface without affecting the geometry. Finally, through the dichotomy method, we deduce the most suitable offset value, which allows us to be more conservative on the translated shape, and be more precise for the same pre-defined admissible error. In order to allow for the geometry to freely deform, we didn't apply the surface constraint at every iteration. Instead, we waited the geometry until it passes by a threshold surface S_{osc} , and we kept on applying the constraint until the surface is included in the interval of the admissible surfaces that is $]S_{ref} - err * S_{ref}; S_{ref} + err * S_{ref}[$. However, like any other constraint, the surface constraint generally end up without reaching the theoretical minimum, and thus, a compromise must be found in order to apply this constraint that is now indispensable.

3.2. SoftBlocking

The minimization of the objective function, might theoretically lead to the modification of the sizes of

the inlets and outlets of the problem. This is, for instance, the case of ducted flows, where the inlets and outlets have big impacts on the evolution of the objective function. At first, rigid blocking was a trivial solution. Although we succeeded in maintaining the positions of the fluid entries and exits, we broke the smoothness on the duct, and created a sudden change in the geometry. That's why we opted for softblocking, where the more it is far from the inlet-outlet, the more the interface is free to move. At each node (x_{node}, y_{node}) where we want to block the connections, we created two circles of diameters d_{V_c} and d_{δ_s} . Inside each circle, we created a scalar function that at each node takes the value of the distance between the node and the blocked node following:

$$d = \sqrt{(x_{node} - x)^2 + (y_{node} - y)^2} \quad (29)$$

For the control velocity, we sought for a filter that is null near the interface, and that reaches 1 steeply and smoothly towards d_{V_c} . The most convenient filter was a hyperbolic tangent one defined as follows:

$$Coef_{V_c} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} * \tanh \left(2.1 * \tan \left(-\frac{\pi}{2} + \pi * \frac{d}{d_{V_c} + \epsilon_1} + \epsilon_2 \right) \right) \quad (30)$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are two small values that we added to avoid discontinuities in the control velocity blocking zone. Here we set $\epsilon_1 = 0.001$ and $\epsilon_2 = 0.005$. For the surface constraint, the filter is exactly null at the interface, but it increases quicker and smoother to reach d_S with $d_{V_c} > d_{\delta_s}$. The most convenient filter was also hyperbolic tangent but defined as:

$$Coef_{\delta_s} = \tanh \left(1.1 * \tan \left(\pi * \frac{d}{2 * d_{\delta_s} + \epsilon_3} \right) \right) \quad (31)$$

where ϵ_3 is also a small values that we added to avoid discontinuities in surface constraint blocking zone. And here we set $\epsilon_3 = 5e^{-5}$.

For smooth deformation of the interface, our experiments showed that the best is to set d_{V_c} equal 1/40 of the distance orthogonal to the inlet-outlet we are blocking, and that d_{δ_s} fits the most when it is equal to $1.8 * d_{V_c}$. But these diameters remain dependant on the geometry, and it's always better to re-tune them case by case.

4. General Algorithm

Figure 3 shows the general algorithm of the topology optimization we applied. Going from the initial

Figure 3: General Algorithm of Topology Optimization

shape, we start by solving the primal and adjoint systems. The state and adjoint equations allows us to compute the control velocity that will be an input for the advection solver that will take in charge moving the interface in the direction of the steepest gradient of the objective function. Automatic re-meshing here is crucial in order to capture the interface with the highest precision possible. If the displacement of each nodes contributes equally to the minimization of the objective function, then we got our converged solution. If not, we apply the surface constraint and re-mesh again for precision. Then we re-iterate until convergence.

5. Numerical Benchmark : Design of a Bend Pipe

The design of a Bend Pipe has already been studied by [11][12][2][13]. The design domain is a 1x1 square with an inlet and an outlet of 0.2, centered at 0.8 from the bottom left corner respectively on the left and bottom side of the design domain as shown in figure 4. The inlet velocity has a parabolic profile whose equation, in a system of x and y axes centered on the bottom corner and merged with the edges of the square, is $U_x = 20(y - 0.7)(y - 0.8)$. At the outlet we consider a reference pressure of zero, and constraint the outgoing flow to be in the vertical direction. At the walls, as for the solid domain that will appear later, we consider a no-slip condition for the velocity and free pressure. The kinematic viscosity is 0.044, which leads to a Reynolds number 0.2 based on the averaged inlet velocity.

The starting geometry is composed of regularly distributed circles, in order to assure that there isn't any guess of what could be the final solution. The total surface occupied by the fluid in this configuration corresponds to 25% of the design domain corresponding to a quarter torus connecting the inlet to the outlet. This will indeed serve as a surface reference for the

Figure 4: Design a of Bend Pipe Case Setup

rest of the problem with an admissible error on the final surface of 1%. The surface threshold before applying the surface constraint is 0.2525. The descent factor that multiplies the control velocity is 3. And the thickness of the Dirac model applied is equal to twice the minimum mesh size at the interface.

For the meshing, we started with a domain divided into three regions: The fluid and solid regions with interface between them. Since Dirichlet boundary conditions are imposed in the solid domain, no computation is taking place in this region, so we may mesh it coarsely. The mesh in the fluid domain is finer, and should be chosen in a way to ensure convergence of the Navier-Stokes Solution. The fluid-solid interface is the most critical region of the domain. It is important to have precise tracking of the interface when it is advected in order to not lose the desired shape and avoid instabilities. So here is where we make mesh adaptation and where we have the finer mesh with a minimum element size of 0.0001. Finally, the blocking functions of the control velocity and surface displacement are calculated on a distance of 0.025 and 0.045 near the frame, so a relatively fine mesh is applied there. In total, we have a sum of 21500 triangular anisotropic elements in all the design domain.

Beginning with three mesh adaptations, we then launch the CFD simulations. The first CFD simulation (done before any shape deformation), takes about ten iterations to converge. Then, due to velocity and pressure interpolations and to the small displacement per iteration of the interface, steady-state solution is

Figure 5: Design a of Bend Pipe Case Setup

reached after two to three iterations. The convergence criteria being an admissible error of 0.05% on the velocity.

Shape convergence is reached after 140 iterations. The evolution of the objective function with respect of the number of iterations is shown in figure 5. For several values of the objective function, we can also follow the shape evolution.

First of all, it is important to note that, contrarily to an intuitive guess, the optimal shape is not a quarter torus connecting the inlet to outlet, but instead, it is an almost straight channel. According to [6], this can be explained as follows: If a prescribed amount of fluid is to be transported in a pipe, the shears in the fluid are large when the pipe is thin and, conversely, small when the pipe is wide. Since the dissipated power in Stokes flow is due to shears only, an optimal flow pipe is preferably short and wide.

6. Conclusion and Perspectives

In conclusion, we described in this article the procedure we followed to build a numerical framework for topology optimization. Going from the Level-Set method coupled with anisotropic mesh adaptation for capturing the interface, we reached sensitivity computation based on the continuous adjoint method, that led us through moving the interface in the optimal direction.

In order to validate our numerical benchmark, three test cases has been studied: the design of a Bend Pipe, of a Dual Pipe, and of a Four Terminal Device. We launched the optimizations going from regular geometries as a started position, to more complex

starting geometries as a design domain full of circles. These test cases proved the reliability and robustness of our algorithm, even though the second test case showed the dependency of the method on the starting geometry. They also helped us to touch that the minimization of the pumping power for a fluidic device, requires at most to shorten the ducts and to make them as wide as possible. Indeed, the results showed that generally, the most optimal shape is the shortest and widest possible duct connecting each inlet to an outlet.

Even though reliable and robust, our algorithm have several limitations. Until now, we only deal with incompressible laminar flows, and steady state problems. Regarding our future work, we aim to tackle heat exchange problems. We also aim to deal with multi-phase flows, which combines variable densities and unsteadiness of the flow. The additional terms and equations, will be mirrored into complexity in the derivation of the sensitivity. Before the last, we wish to gradually increase the Reynolds number of the flow. And finally, we will switch to three dimension problems.

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References

- [1] M. P. Bendsoe, O. Sigmund, *Topology Optimization*, Springer, 2004. doi:10.1007/978-3-662-05086-6.
- [2] T. Borrvall, J. Petersson, Topology optimization of fluids in stokes flow, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids* 41 (1) (2003) 77–107. arXiv:https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/flid.426, doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/flid.426.
- [3] T. Coupez, Metric construction by length distribution tensor and edge based error for anisotropic adaptive meshing, *Journal of Computational Physics* 230 (7) (2011) 2391–2405. doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2010.11.041.
- [4] G. Kunert, R. Verfürth, Edge residuals dominate a posteriori error estimates for linear finite element methods on anisotropic triangular and tetrahedral meshes, *Numerische Mathematik* 86 (2000) 283–303. doi:10.1007/PL00005407.
- [5] T. Coupez, E. Hachem, Solution of high-Reynolds incompressible flow with stabilized finite element and adaptive anisotropic meshing, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 267 (2013) 65–85. doi:10.1016/j.cma.2013.08.004.
- [6] E. Hachem, B. Rivaux, T. Kloczko, H. Dignonet, T. Coupez, Stabilized finite element method for incompressible flows with high Reynolds number, *Journal of Computational Physics* 229 (23) (2010) Pages 8643–8665. doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2010.07.030.
- [7] M. Sussman, P. Smereka, S. Osher, A level set approach for computing solutions to incompressible two-phase flow, *Journal of Computational Physics* 114 (1) (1994) 146–159. doi:https://doi.org/10.1006/jcph.1994.1155.
- [8] M. Khalloufi, Y. Mesri, R. Valette, E. Massoni, E. Hachem, High fidelity anisotropic adaptive variational multiscale method for multiphase flows with surface tension, *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 307 (2016) 44–67. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2016.04.014.
- [9] L. Marioni, M. Khalloufi, F. Bay, E. Hachem, Two-fluid flow under the constraint of external magnetic field, *International Journal of Numerical Methods for Heat and Fluid Flow* 27 (11) (2017) 2565 – 2581. doi:10.1108/HFF-09-2016-0371.
- [10] C. Bahbah, M. Khalloufi, A. Larcher, Y. Mesri, T. Coupez, R. Valette, E. Hachem, Conservative and adaptive level-set method for the simulation of two-fluid flows, *Computers and Fluids* 191 (2019) 104223. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2019.06.022.
- [11] X.-B. Duan, Y.-C. Ma, R. Zhang, Shape-topology optimization for navier–stokes problem using variational level set method, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 222 (2) (2008) 487–499. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cam.2007.11.016.
- [12] M. Abdelwahed, M. Hassine, M. Masmoudi, Optimal shape design for fluid flow using topological perturbation technique, *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications* 356 (2) (2009) 548–563. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmaa.2009.02.045.
- [13] A. Gersborg, O. Sigmund, R. Haber, Topology optimization of channel flow problems, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization* 30 (2005) 181–192. doi:10.1007/s00158-004-0508-7.